

THE ASSESSMENT OF TEMPORAL CHANGE OF POPULATION IN MARATHWADA REGION: A GEOGRAPHICAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT:

Human Population is dynamic phenomenon having change periodically and spatially. In fact, increase the number of people in specific period at particular region is called as population change. Also, human population is widely distributed all over the world, but, human population distribution pattern has unevenly observed in the world. As global level, big population is habited in Asian countries and less population is settled in North Pole, South Pole, desert region, Amazon River wet region etc. Place and period is determinant factor of population change. Besides, Births, deaths and migration are also relevant factor of population change. In 1983, According to researcher Singh and Chaturvedi, the change or growth of population is a factor associated with man's occupation, cultural background, historical events and political ideology. Change is rule of nature and population change is general term of human population. About India, human population has been steadily increasing from 361 million in 1951 to 1210 million in 2011. Today, India is top most population country at global level. Hence, study the change of human population is important for government and scholar. This research paper is attempt to assessment of temporal change of population in Marathwada region. There is comparative study of year wise population of Marathwada region.

KEYWORDS: *Population, Births, India, Marathwada region etc.*

INTRODUCTION

Human Population is dynamic phenomenon having change periodically and spatially. In fact, increase the number of people in specific period at particular region is called as population change. Also, human population is widely distributed all over the world, but, human population distribution pattern has unevenly observed in the world. As global level, big population is habited in Asian countries and less population is settled in North Pole, South Pole, desert region, Amazon River wet region etc. Place and period is determinant factor of population change. Besides, Births, deaths and migration are also relevant factor of population change. In 1983, According to researcher Singh and Chaturvedi, the change or growth of population is a factor associated with man's occupation, cultural background, historical events and political ideology. Change is rule of nature and population change is general term of human population. About India, human population has been steadily increasing from 361 million in 1951 to 1210 million in 2011. Today, India is top most population country at global level. As per the 2011 census of India, the total population of Marathwada region is about 13659798 persons, which noticed widely distribution of human population.

STUDY AREA

The Marathwada region chosen for the research study the assessment of temporal change of population. Marathwada region is South Central part of Maharashtra state, mainly located in Godavari river valley between 17° 35' North to 20° 40' North latitude and 74° 40' East to 78° 15' East longitude. As report of 2011 district Census handbook, about 13659798 persons have habited in the Marathwada Hingoli.etc.

OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the research paper are as under:

1. To study the temporal change of Human Population in the study region.
2. To examine the change of Human population in the study region.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY

The present research work is based on secondary data which is gathered from distinct census handbook from 1951 to 2011 year. Different books, district census report, district socio-economic Volume-57, No.1 (IV) 2023

abstract, government report etc. are used for investigation in research. The investigation and interpretation of research data includes theoretical approach. All the data has been collected at district level. The other right cartographic methods have also been used. The distribution is shown with the help of tables and maps.

TEMPORAL CHANGE OF POPULATION IN MARATHAWADA REGION

Marathwada region is situated in the south-eastern part of Maharashtra covering an area of 64639 sq. km. According to the 2011 Census of India, Marathwada has a total population of about 13659798 persons, which is 16.84% of the state's population. In fact, according to the 1951 census, Marathwada had a population of about 5.11 million which steadily increased to 18.73 million people from 1951 to 2011. Gradually, the population increased to 6.30 million in 1961, 8.06 million in 1971, 9.75 million in 1981, 12.8 million in 1991, 15.59 million in 2001, 18.73 million in 2011, etc. year

I. Table 1

Marathwada Region: Growth of Population from 1951 to 2011

Sr.No.	Year	Total Population (in million)	Absolute Increase in the Decade (in million)	Growth in Percent	Annual Growth Rate (Percent)
1	1951	5.11	--	--	--
2	1961	6.3	1.19	23.24	2.32
3	1971	8.06	1.76	27.96	2.8
4	1981	9.74	1.69	20.92	2.09
5	1991	12.8	3.06	31.37	3.14
6	2001	15.59	2.79	21.78	2.18
7	2011	18.73	3.14	20.16	2.02

Sources: Census of India, 1961-2011.

Table no. 2 and Figure no. 2 and Figure no. 3 shows Population growth in Marathwada division from 1951 to 2011.

In the year 1951, Marathwada region had a population of 5.11 million, an absolute growth of 1.19 million was recorded between 1951-1961, where the population rose from 5.11 million in 1951 to 6.30 million in 1961 and grew at an average annual rate of 2.32%. In percentage terms, Marathwada Division added about 23.24 percent of its human population to its total population during the years 1951 to 1961. Where, between the years 1951 to 1961, high birth rate, illiteracy and economic backwardness affected the natural growth of the population.

In the year 1961, the population of Marathwada region was 6.30 million, the population recorded an absolute increase of 1.76 million during 1961–1971, where the population was 6.30 million in 1961 to 8.06 million in 1971 and grew at an average annual rate of 2.80%. In percentage terms, about 27.96

percent of the human population was added to the total population of Marathwada region during the years 1961 to 1971, where between 1961 and 1971, development in food supply and medical facilities led to a rapid decline in mortality and high population growth.

In 1971, Marathwada region had a population of 8.06 million, with an absolute population growth of 1.69 million during the period 1971–1981, where the population from 8.06 million in 1971 to 9.74 million in 1981 grew at an average annual rate of 2.09%. In percentage terms, Marathwada region added about 20.92 percent human population to the total population during the years 1971 to 1981. Between the years 1971 to 1981, in Marathwada region, the percentage of population growth has decreased, the birth rate has declined and the standard of living has improved, with better life expectancy, better socio-economic conditions, developed medical facilities and better literacy levels.

In 1981, Marathwada region had a population of 9.74 million, with an absolute population growth of 3.06 million recorded during 1981–1991, where the population grew from 9.74 million in 1981 to 12.80 million in 1991 with an average annual growth rate of 3.14%. In percentage terms, the total population of Marathwada Division increased by about 31.37 percent during the year 1981 to 1991. Positive changes in the standard of living, life expectancy, socio-economic conditions, medical facilities etc. in Marathwada region during the period 1981 to 1991 have resulted in excellent population growth.

In 1991, the population of Marathwada region was 12.08 million, with an absolute population growth of 2.79 million recorded during 1991–2001, where the population increased from 12.08 million in 1991 to 15.59 million in 2001, growing at an average annual rate of 2%. In percentage terms, the total human population of Maharashtra increased by about 21.78 percent during the years 1991 to 2001. Between 1991 and 2001, due to increasing levels of literacy, people have reached a higher socio-cultural level, the government's anti-population growth policies have led to declining birth rates and declining death rates.

In the year 2001, the population of Marathwada was 15.59 million, during 2001–2011 the population recorded an absolute increase of 3.14 million, where the population was 15.59 million in 2001 to 18.73 million in 2011 and grew at an average annual rate of 2.02 %. In percentage terms, the total population of Maharashtra increased by about 20.16 percent during the year 2001 to 2011. Between 2001 and 2011, due to the success of Maharashtra government's birth control policies, the birth rate was slightly under control, resulting in a lower growth rate in this decade than in the previous decade.

However, the population of Marathwada region in the year 1951 was 5.11 million, it increased to 18.73 million in the year 2011, which is the highest population growth of Marathwada region at the state level.

ASSESSMENT OF TEMPORAL CHANGE OF POPULATION

- 1) The population of Marathwada region in the year 1951 was 5.11 million, it increased to 18.73 million in the year 2011.
- 2) The population of Marathwada region is decade wise average population about 10.90 million from 1951 year to 2011 year.
- 3) The population of Marathwada region is decade wise averagely absolute increased about 2.27 million from 1951 year to 2011 year.
- 4) The population of Marathwada region is decade wise averagely growth about 24.24 percent from 1951 year to 2011 year.
- 5) The population of Marathwada region is annually growth about 2.4 percent from 1951 year to 2011 year.
- 6) Highly growth of human population in percentage (31.37 percent) is observed in from 1981 year to 1991 year.
- 7) Less growth of human population in percentage (20.16 percent) is observed in from 2001 year to 2011 year.

CONCLUSION

Human Population is dynamic phenomenon having change periodically and spatially. Human population is widely distributed all over the world, but, human population distribution pattern has unevenly observed in the world. As per the 2011 census of India, the total population of Marathwada region is about 13659798 persons, which noticed widely distribution of human population. The population of Marathwada region in the year 1951 was 5.11 million, it increased to 18.73 million in the year 2011, which is the highest population growth of Marathwada region at the state level. The population of Marathwada region is annually growth about 2.4 percent from 1951 year to 2011 year. Highly growth of human population in percentage (31.37 percent) is observed in from 1981 year to 1991 year, whereas, less growth of human population in percentage (20.16 percent) is observed in from 2001 year to 2011 year. Life expectancy, socio-economic conditions, medical facilities, high birth rate, illiteracy and economic backwardness affected the growth of the population.

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